

Referral Pattern of Cancer Patients to a Young Palliative Care Unit in Southwest, Nigeria

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Article information

Date Submitted: 28/12/2020.

Date Accepted: 11/10/2021

Date Published: 25/11/2021

ABSTRACT

Studies have shown that palliative care referral is not done as often and as early as required. In order to identify the potential barriers, an audit of current referral pattern is required towards planning for efficient palliative care services. This study aims to determine the pattern of referral of patients for palliative care and the outcome of care provided. A retrospective cross-sectional study, reviewing records of all inpatients from 1st June 2016 to 30th October 2018 at the health information's department and palliative care unit of Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital, Sagamu, Ogun state.. Data was manually analyzed and results are presented in prose, tables and figures. There were a total of 10,186 in-patients admissions during the 29-months review period. The number of patients diagnosed with cancer was 309, out of which only forty-two (42, 13.6%) were referred to the palliative care unit. General surgeons referred most patients; (21, 50%), the Gynecologist (14, 33.3%), Internal medicine physicians (3, (7.1%), Haematology (2, (4.8%), while Orthopaedic surgeons and Paediatricians referred (1, (2.4%) each. All referred patients had no other intercurrent illness. In conclusion; referral pattern documented at our health facility showed that so far only cancer patients were referred. It was noted that the percentage being referred is still very low. Most clinicians would benefit from education on who should be referred for palliative care and how early so as to improve the quality of life of patients who need such services

Keywords: Palliative care, Referral pattern, Cancer patients

INTRODUCTION

The word palliative in Latin means “caring”.¹ Palliative care is an approach that improves the quality of life of patients and their families facing the problem associated with life-threatening illnesses,

through the prevention and relief of suffering by means of early identification, impeccable assessment, treatment of pain and other problems, physical, psychosocial and spiritual.¹ Palliative care begins when illness is diagnosed

How to cite this article

Fatungase OM, Ayoade BA, Shoyemi RO, Ekor OE, Soyannwo OA. Referral Pattern of Cancer Patients to a Young Palliative Care Unit in Southwest, Nigeria. J Biomed Res Clin Pract:2021;4(4):63-68. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6066218

Access to the article

website: <http://www.jbrcp.net>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6066218

and continues regardless of whether the patient receives treatment directed at the disease.^{1,2}

It is required for a wide range of diseases and majority of adults in need of this care have chronic diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, chronic respiratory diseases, HIV AIDs and diabetes, kidney failure, chronic liver disease, multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's disease, rheumatoid arthritis, neurological disease, dementia, congenital anomalies and drug-resistant tuberculosis.²

Pain is one of the most frequent and serious symptoms experienced by patients in need of palliative care. The need for pain relief at an early stage is an ethical duty towards relieving suffering and respect for the dignity of patients. It is estimated that 40 million people are in need of palliative care every year and that 78% of them live in low- and middle-income countries.³ Although palliative care was official recognized in Nigeria in 1993, it is yet to be fully integrated into patient care due to obstacles met with health care practitioners and health policies in the country.⁴ It is also noted to be rudimentary in most African countries as most health practitioners have poor knowledge of palliative care. As such individualistic approach is what obtains even in the management of terminal cancer patients.⁵ In a study involving 234 countries, territories and areas, it was reported that palliative care services was only well integrated in 20 countries, while 42% had no palliative care services and a further 32% had only isolated palliative care services.⁶ Similarly, 83% of the world's population in 2011 lived in countries with low to non-existent access to opioid pain relief.⁶

Dealing with symptoms of any painful or life limiting illness can be a challenging task for any health care professional. Palliative care provides an answer and has a vital role to play in the management of patients whose very existence is under serious threat or may well be compounded by pain and other distressing symptoms.^{6,7}

The time to referral is noted as the time calculated from the first day of recent in-patient admission to the day of palliative care referral. Early referral patients were those referred within one week of hospital admission, while

late referral patients were those later than one week.^{8,9}

The central theme of palliative care is to provide a reasonable and meaningful quality of life.⁶ Therefore, efforts directed at improving the quality of palliative care services are of paramount importance to the very integrity of health care professionals and the health care system. The aim of this study was to determine the pattern of referral of patients for palliative care and the outcome of care provided. It is hoped that this survey will make significant contribution to improving the plight of dying patients and their families in our health facility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A retrospective cross-sectional study was carried out reviewing all the in-patients records from the hospital's medical records and those referred to palliative care unit of Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital. The data was collected from June 1st 2016 up to October 30th 2018 using a purposed-designed proforma. Data collected included: patient demographics, date of recent in-patient hospital admission, time- interval between recent day in-patient hospital admission and referral to Palliative Care Unit, presenting complaint, diagnosis, stages of cancer, referral-to death interval, location of death and management outcome. The time to refer to palliative care interval was operationalized as the time calculated from the recent day of in-patient hospital admission to palliative care unit. Early patient referrals were those referred within one week of hospital admission while late patient referrals were those later than one week. Data was entered and analyzed manually. Results are presented in prose, tables and figures.

RESULTS

There were a total of 10,186 inpatient admissions during the 29 months review period. The number of patients diagnosed as having different forms of cancer were 309, out of which only forty two (42; 13.6%) were referred to be seen by the palliative care unit of the hospital. Table 1

shows the demographic data.

The range from time of referral to palliative care (interval between recent day of hospital admission and referral to Palliative Care Unit) and this was one day to 265days with mean of 36.36±10 days. Figure 1, showed the presenting complaints. Intractable or uncontrolled pain was the most common presenting complains.

It should be noted that 100% of cases referred were cancer patients. Table II showed the distribution of the cancer cases that were referred for palliative care. Most of the patients (42.9%) had breast cancer and were referred at advanced stages (stage 4 mostly) of their illnesses.

Table I: Demographic data of Respondents

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age ± SD	46.48±13.70	
Gender	Female	34
	Male	8
	Total	42
Ethnicity	Yoruba	35
	Ibo	5
	Hausa	2
	Total	42
Religion	Christianity	27
	Islam	15
	Traditional	0
	Others	0
	Total	42
Education	Primary	5
	Secondary	19
	Tertiary	17
	Postgraduate	1
	Total	42

Figure 1: Patients' Presenting Complaint

Key: *UP*-Uncontrolled pain, *BS*-Breast Swellings, *ABS* -Abdominal Swelling

BPO- Bilateral Pitting Oedema, *UPS* - Upper limb swellings,

GBW -. Generalised body Weakness, *PPG*- Paraplegia, *DB* - Difficulty in Breathing

JD- Jaundice, *VM* - Vomiting, *AB VD*- Abnormal vagina discharge,

LWS -Passage of Loose watery Stool

Table 2 : Distribution of the cancer cases

Cases	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Breast	18	42.9
Ovary	7	16.7
Uterus	4	10
Liver	3	7.1
Stomach	3	7.1
Cervix	2	4.76
Leukaemia	2	4.76
Vulvo-varginal	1	2.38
Kidney	1	2.38
Osteosarcoma	1	2
Total	42	100

Majority 21 (50%) of the cases referred were from General surgeons followed by Gynaecology as shown in Figure 2.

Referral time to death interval ranges from few hours to forty-five days with a mean 22.45 ± 15.33 days. A total of eleven patients (26.2%) died while on hospital admission while thirty-one patients (73.8%) were discharged home. During hospital admission, pain control was the main reason for referral to the palliative care unit. And this was achieved after proper clinical assessment of the patient by the administration of oral morphine in graded doses, antidepressants, steroids and or local anaesthetics. Other palliative care services rendered were spiritual (prayers), psychological and physical support. Apart from this, some patients received medical intervention such as Oxygen therapy [16: 38.1%], antimicrobial therapy (30, 71.4%), and chemotherapy (42, 100%), tumour debulking surgery (20, 47.6%), blood transfusion [32: 76.2%] and close tube thoracotomy drainage [19: 45.2%]. The mean age of death was 22.45 ± 14.08 years.

Figure 2: Referral Pattern of Patients that required Palliative Care from different Specialties

DISCUSSION

Three hundred and nine (309) patients were diagnosed as having different forms of cancer, out of which only forty two (42; 13.6%) were referred to the palliative care unit of the hospital. This showed that most of the patients with cancer were not getting access to palliative care services at the appropriate time in their disease trajectory. Reasons for delayed referral could not be determined because study was retrospective.

Majority (34, 80.95%), of the referred palliative patients were females and breast cancer (18, 42.9%) represented the commonest cases referred. This could be due to the fact that breast malignancy is the commonest cause of cancer among female.⁷ Demographic findings from this study showed that majority belonged to Yoruba ethnic group probably because the study was carried out in south-western part of Nigeria where Yorubas form the dominant ethnic group.

Majority of the individuals referred to the palliative care service had solid tumour metastatic diseases (95%) while few (5%) had haematological malignancies (leukaemia), this is similar to the study by Regina M.⁸

In our study majority (66.7%) of the referred cases were late-referrals, which implied that patients had shortened opportunities for palliative care services. Previous studies have pointed out the importance of timely referral in achieving the goals of palliative care consultation. Late referrals have been consistently reported as barrier to accomplishing the desired benefits of palliative care such as provision of early pain control, physical, psychological, emotional support which could have helped in blunting the impact of the disease thereby helping to prolong the life through overall improved quality of life and efficient symptom control.^{9,10,11}

Studies have shown that palliative care referrals are not done as often and as early as required.^{10, 11, 12} Early referral to palliative care not only facilitates timely diagnosis and treatment of symptoms, but also minimizes care-giver distress and aggressive measures at the end of life.^{6,9}

When considering association between referral-to death

interval, a referral-to death interval of less than seven days is considered to be “late” referral in palliative care, based on the perception of the family members and the physicians regarding the optimum period needed for achieving the goals of hospice care in some studies.^{12,13,14}

Results from our study showed that 3(27.3%) were referred less than seven days before death, which is similar to the results obtained in the study by Jissy *et al*¹⁵

The time interval between palliative care referral and death may play a role in determining the last place of care and location of death of patients referred to palliative teams. Regina M,⁸ showed that individuals who were referred to palliative care more often were from intensive care setting, meanwhile patients referred in our study were from general wards, while some are likely to die at home because majority were admitted mainly for chemotherapy. There was no record of palliative care follow-up to determine whether those that were discharged home had home-based palliative care.

Dealing with symptoms of any painful or life limiting illness can be a challenging task for any health care professional. Palliative care has a vital role to play in the management of patients whose very existence is under serious threat or may well be compounded by pain and other distressing symptoms.^{8,16}

Limitation

This study only examined the influence of in-patient palliative care consultation services, the effect of an outpatient program has not been established. Outpatient palliative care actually may decrease in-patient admission and improve patients' quality of life.

The scope of this study did not cover follow-up palliative care services for those who were discharged home.

CONCLUSION

Patient outcome has close relationship to early referral pattern. It is necessary to re-orientate health practitioners

on how soon to refer patients who require palliative care services thereby improving the quality of life

Conflict of interest: None

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